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Fracture mechanics testing of irradiated RPV steels by means of sub-sized specimens

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Guidelines for Master Curve testing with miniature specimens

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¹ **Nature:** R -Document, report; **DEM** -Demonstrator, pilot, prototype; **DEC** -Websites, patent fillings, videos, etc.; **OTHER**; **ETHICS** -Ethics requirement; **ORDP** -Open Research Data Pilot; **DATA** -data sets, microdata, etc.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Given the sustained interest in the nuclear industry towards continuous optimization of the material testing program in support of structural integrity assessments of nuclear reactor components and safety case substantiation, investigation of the possibility of using fracture toughness data derived from testing miniature specimens has been gaining traction in recent years due to smaller total volume of material required for testing. In particular, extending the use of the ASTM E1921 approach for ascertaining the fracture toughness in the ductile to brittle transition regime to miniature specimens has gained considerable attention.

However, to properly achieve the intended outcomes, several technical barriers need to be overcome. These include (among others), lack of sufficient confidence in the applicability of the basic ASTM E1921 methodology to miniature 4 mm thick (0.16T) CT specimens, a need for better understanding of the limits of applicability of the ASTM E1921 methodology and difficulties in meeting the stringent requirements for specimen fabrication, testing and data validation requirements as mandated by the code procedure, which are relatively more amenable towards larger specimens.

To that end, this technical guidance note has been written to curate the key outcomes, observations and recommendations emerging from the FRACTESUS project to facilitate suitable adaptation of the ASTM E1921 Master curve procedure to accurately ascertain the fracture toughness of RPV steels in the DBTT regime from testing miniature specimens. It outlines selected challenges for demonstrating conformity to the requirements stipulated by ASTM E1921 for validation of results derived from miniature specimens and highlights observations and recommendations to optimise the use of the ASTM E1921 methodology. Furthermore, additional best practices and avenues for perusal and furtherance pertaining to different areas have also been highlighted. These include some empirically justified adjustments that would facilitate a more accurate extrapolation of the test results derived from miniature specimens to estimate the material properties at a component level.

This document also includes a basic overview of the ASTM E1921 Master Curve methodology to help put into context, the outcomes and recommendations emerging from the FRACTESUS project along with the key caveats that need to be taken into consideration. Furthermore, arguments or observations from selected externally published literature pertinent to this work have also been presented for completeness.

It is anticipated that the guidance emerging from the FRACTESUS project as summarised herein this report would help with characterising the fracture toughness of RPV steels in the DBTT regime using results from miniature specimen testing with a high degree of confidence to inform structural integrity assessments of reactor components. It is also envisioned that the approaches developed within the FRACTESUS project can be suitably leveraged to support continuous optimisation of future miniature specimen testing programs through robust dialectic reasoning. This may consider the relative influence and interplay of the different control parameters affecting the overall accuracy of the fracture behaviour characterisation using miniature specimens based on the observations and arguments presented in the dedicated FRACTESUS deliverables summarised herein this report.

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1 ABBREVIATIONS

a	Crack length
a_0	Initial crack length
b_0	Remaining ligament length
ASME	American Society of Mechanical Engineers (body issuing codes/standards)
ASTM	American Society for Testing and Materials (body issuing codes / standards)
B	Specimen thickness
BM	Base metal
B_N	Net thickness
CT	Compact tension, same as C(T)
DBTT	Ductile-to-brittle transition temperature
IAEA	International Atomic Energy Authority
K_e	Fracture toughness parameter (see ASTM Standard E1921-21)
K_{IC}	Plane strain (elastic) mode-I fracture toughness
K_{Jc}	Elastic-plastic equivalent stress intensity factor derived from J_c
K_{Jc1T}	Size corrected value of K_{Jc} (see ASTM Standard E1921-21)
J_e	Elastic part of the J-integral
J_p	Plastic part of the J-integral
J_c	J-integral at onset of cleavage fracture
LLD	Load line displacement
LSY	Large scale yielding
MC	Master curve.
MCT	Mini-CT specimen
N	Number of valid K_{Jc} data in a master curve analysis
NPP	Nuclear power plant
P_f	Probability of failure
RPV	Reactor pressure vessel
SE(B)	Single edged bending
SSY	Small scale yielding
StDev	Standard deviation
T	Temperature
T_0	Temperature at which median fracture toughness is $100 \text{ MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$ using Master curve analysis
$T_{0,scrn}$	Inhomogeneity screening temperature as defined in ASTM E1921-21
W	Specimen width
WM	Weld metal
YS	Yield strength
$\sum(r_i \cdot n_i)$	Validity criterion of a master curve test series (section 10.3 3 of ASTM E1921)

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3 INTRODUCTION

3.1 Background to the project

Accurate evaluation of RPV steel fracture toughness in the DBTT regime is a pressing concern for nuclear reactor operators worldwide to inform nuclear reactor pressure vessel integrity assessment for substantiation of life extension arguments underpinning the safety cases. Although ASTM E399 [1] provides a route to characterise K_{IC} , it cannot be readily adopted for fracture toughness characterization in the transition temperature region for several reasons. To begin with, ASTM E399 requires large specimens for valid results, which leads to prohibitive testing and manufacturing costs of the specimen. Also, as is well known (e.g. see [2]), in the DBTT region, micro-mechanisms of cleavage fracture result in highly scattered cleavage toughness data when compared to the lower shelf region. Consequently, rather than single value of toughness at a particular temperature, the material has a toughness distribution which thus warrants a statistical analysis for accurate characterization.

The ASTM E1921 [3] Master curve (MC) approach has evolved as a promising methodology to evaluate the fracture toughness of the RPV steels in the DBTT regime and has reinforced the possibility of testing miniature specimens. In particular, small specimen testing, supported by a master curve-based analysis of the data can greatly optimise the effort needed for characterisation of irradiated material properties and allow testing of product forms and components of geometries from which standard, large specimens cannot be extracted. Furthermore, since up to eight 0.16T CTs can be cut from a single Charpy specimen, use of 0.16T CTs allows the conversion of historically Charpy-based reactor pressure vessel surveillance schemes into schemes providing toughness data [4].

The FRACTESUS Horizon 2020 project combines European and International efforts aiming to establish a more secure foundation for fracture toughness measurement using miniature specimens and to develop and demonstrate the procedures necessary to achieve the changes to current codes and standards required to address the various national regulatory authority concerns about data derived from small specimens [4], [5].

Although promising results have been reported previously with regards to the use of miniature specimens for evaluation of the ductile to brittle transition temperature [6], there remain some concerns in relation to their application to specimens as small as 0.16T CT specimens as noted in the FRACTESUS Deliverable 1.1 [7]. As emphasized in [6], valid K_{IC} is believed to represent a lower limiting value of fracture toughness (for 2% apparent crack extension) and generally accepted as a “size-independent” value. However, obtaining valid fracture toughness values becomes a challenge with the use of sub-sized specimens whereby size effects come into play (except for very brittle materials). Also, as noted in FRACTESUS Technical Memorandum [4], another key concern with use of miniature specimens is that while the toughness measurement from a miniature specimen could be valid in itself, the volume of material tested might be too small to be properly representative of the material considering material homogeneity aspects.

The FRACTESUS project hence aims to investigate the ambiguities and the associated remedial measures required for the accurate extrapolation of the results derived from the application of the ASTM E1921 [3] MC approach for miniature specimens to standardised specimens considering both base metals (which were anticipated to be relatively homogeneous) and welds (which were expected to be less homogeneous).

3.2 Reference geometry

The reference specimen geometry used in the FRACTESUS project was the miniature Compact Tension (CT) specimen, 10 mm x 10 mm x 4 mm, (~0.16T CT) as shown in Figure 1. The CT specimen geometry is considered ideal since historic surveillance capsules include Charpy impact specimens and up to eight 0.16T CT specimens can be manufactured from a single broken Charpy specimen as highlighted in the FRACTESUS Technical Memorandum [8].

Figure 1. Four 0.16T CT specimens as extracted from a broken half Charpy impact specimen.

The dimensions used for the 0.16T CT specimen were based on the advice provided in established standards in terms of setting the primary dimensions relative to others as highlighted in FRACTESUS Deliverable 2.1 [9]. The requirements stipulate that the width, W , shall be twice the thickness, B , and initial crack size, a_0 , half the width. The ratio of specimen height to width, H/W , is defined as 1.2. Total width of the specimen, W_{tot} , is $1.25W$.

3.3 Material selection

As part of the FRACTESUS project, six different reactor pressure vessel steels were identified, covering a range of product forms, compositions and transition temperatures. The materials were derived from both eastern and western type reactor pressure vessels and were chosen to have large variance in properties considering the effects of chemical composition, manufacturing methods (plates, forgings and weld metals) and ageing/ irradiation exposure. The reference temperature T_0 of unirradiated materials according to previous tests ranged from $-134\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ to $+8\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$.

All of these steels had been tested previously in the form of large specimens, often in more than one specimen geometry the details of which are available in FRACTESUS

Deliverable 2.1 [9]. Sections or specimens of these steels were acquired by FRACTESUS and manufactured into 4 mm thick (0.16T) miniature compact tension specimens.

The materials considered for this investigation are highlighted below in Table 1. For brevity, only the high-level information is presented. The reader is advised to refer to FRACTESUS deliverables [5], [9] and [10] for more details pertaining to the source, chemical composition, mechanical properties and the rationale behind the selection of the chosen materials.

Table 1. Materials tested under the FRACTESUS project.

Material	Type	Provider	Orientation	Description
15Kh2MFAA	BM	HZDR	L-S	Original RPV of NPP Greifswald unit 8, extracted from the forged core shell ring 0.3.1, original manufacturing technology (Skoda)
A533B JRQ	BM	NRI	T-L	IAEA reference steel, produced by Kawasaki Steel Corp., hot rolled plate (BOF-LRF), block 5JRQ56B1, normalization 900 °C/1h/oil quenching, tempering 665 °C/12h/air cooling, stress release 620 °C/40h
HSSI-73W	WM	SCK-CEN	T-L	High-Cu weld, produced within 5 th irradiation series in Heavy-Section Steel Irradiation program (HSSI), USA, welded blocks 1220 x 218 mm, AC tandem arc, heat treatment 607 °C/40h/air cooling
SA508 Cl.3	BM	CIEMAT	R-C	Original RPV head of Zorita NPP, forging according to ASME S II A, Subsection III-NB
ANP-5	WM	FRA-G	T-L	High-Cu weld, produced by Klöckner, NiCrMo1 submerged arc welding wire and modified LW320/330 powder
A533B LUS	BM	SCK-CEN	T-L	Round Robin material of JSPS with low upper shelf energy due to high P and S contents; Hot rolled plate according to ASTM standard for A533B Class 1

4 OVERVIEW OF KEY PROJECT OBSERVATIONS AND OUTCOMES

4.1 Introduction

The ASTM E1921 [3] Master Curve methodology targets three main issues of fracture characterization within the DBTT namely, the scatter of the results, the dependency of fracture toughness on the test temperature, and the influence of the specimen thickness [11]. The E1921 methodology also provides a route to quantify the uncertainty in the estimate of reference temperature T_0 characterising the ductile to brittle transition based on the number and distribution of the toughness measurements in a dataset and the approach to be used for ascertaining a conservative estimate of the lower bound taking the uncertainty into account (the margin-adjusted bounds).

However, successful adoption of this approach for miniature specimens requires investigation, evaluation and resolution of several uncertainties, which include (but are not limited to) test temperature, specimen size, loading rate, initial crack length and material homogeneity effects.

The sections to follow will provide an account of the outcomes from the different strands associated with the FRACTESUS project targeting the above areas. The sections have been categorised and presented to a suitable level of abstraction that would allow relatively easy adaptation of the knowledge for future investigations. The key constraints and caveats underscoring each of the areas and specific observations made in relation to these within the FRACTESUS project have also been identified, which can be used as suitable starting points to optimise the use of the ASTM E1921 methodology for miniature specimens.

For completeness, an overview of basic philosophy and theoretical basis underpinning the ASTM E1921 methodology is presented in Section 4.2 which will help put into context, the outcomes and recommendations emerging from the FRACTESUS project. **Readers who are fully familiar with the basic approach underpinning ASTM E1921 methodology may skip section 4.2 and go to section 4.3.**

4.2 Overview of ASTM E1921 Master Curve methodology.

The ASTM Master curve approach is based on the premise that the fracture behaviour of ferritic steels can be categorised into distinct lower shelf – transition – upper shelf regions and that the failure in the DBTT regime is dominated by cleavage fracture. It then follows that in the DBTT regime, there may be little to no stable microcrack growth in the structure and that propagation of a microcrack under applied load is likely to be unstable with little energy expenditure and plastic deformation at the crack tip, potentially leading to sudden catastrophic failure.

On this basis, the ASTM E1921 Master curve approach [3] uses a Weibull model to describe the statistical cumulative probability of failure p_f for an arbitrarily chosen specimen from a large population of specimens at or before a given value of the characteristic fracture toughness in the DBTT regime K_{JC} as highlighted below in Equation 1.

$$P_f = 1 - \exp \left\{ - \left[\frac{(K_{JC} - 20)}{(K_0 - 20)} \right]^4 \right\}$$

Equation 1

Here K_0 is the scale parameter which identifies the value of K_{JC} corresponding to a p_f value of 63.2%. For sufficient accuracy, ASTM E1921 methodology requires evaluation of the scale parameter using the K_{JC} results derived from six or more samples.

Furthermore, as noted in [6], the scatter in fracture toughness data in the transition region follows a statistical distribution that is very similar for all ferritic steels with yield strength ranging from 275 to 825 MPa. This is again defined by a three parameter Weibull distribution model underscored by the statistical weakest link theory (which assumes cleavage fracture with a single initiation point) typically used to characterise failure pattern observed in brittle materials. Also, the shape of the fracture toughness vs. temperature curve in the transition region is nearly the same for all ferritic steels (with the only variation being in the relative position of the curve in the temperature axis) provided $-50^\circ\text{C} \leq T - T_0 \leq +50^\circ\text{C}$ [12].

The ASTM E1921 approach uses the following equation to describe the fracture toughness for any probability of failure (P_f) taking into account upper and lower tolerance bounds

$$K_{JC, Pf} = 20 + [\ln(1/(1-P_f))]^{1/4} * \{11+77 * \exp[0.019 * (T - T_0)]\}$$

Equation 2

Here P_f is tolerance bound (e.g. 0.05 for 5%) indicating the percentage of the tested sample population that is likely to provide lower than the estimated K_{JC} value and T_0 is the scale parameter which identifies the ductile-to-brittle transition reference temperature. In order to address the uncertainty in T_0 due to sample size and experimental uncertainties, the ASTM E1921 methodology prescribes the use of a margin adjustment to T_0 to introduce an upwards shift in the tolerance bound curve (Equation 2) using the standard deviation derived from Equation 3 below.

$$\sigma = \left[\frac{\beta^2}{r} + \sigma_{\text{exp}}^2 \right]^{1/2}$$

Equation 3

Where β is the sample size uncertainty factor, r is the total number of uncensored data used to establish T_0 , and σ_{exp} is the contribution of experimental uncertainties (typically 4°C).

Once σ is determined, a margin adjusted T_0 value ($T_{0\text{mar}}$) can be evaluated using T_0 , σ and the 'Z' score for a suitable confidence level 'y' as below [3].

$$T_{0\text{mar}} = T_0 + \sigma(z_y)$$

Equation 4

For 1T specimens, the expression for median fracture toughness $K_{JC(\text{med})}$ ($P_f = 0.5$) for any temperature in the DBTT regime can then be derived from Equation 2 as

$$K_{JC(\text{med})1T} = 30+70*\exp[0.019*(T-T_0)]$$

Equation 5

Thus, the ASTM E1921 approach provides both a mean transition toughness value as well as a distribution around that value. It then follows from Equation 5, that when $T=T_0$, the value of $K_{JC(\text{med})1T}$ is 100 MPa√m. In other words, ASTM E1921 describes T_0 as the reference temperature at which the median of fracture toughness, $K_{JC(\text{med})}$, for a 1T (25.4 mm) thick specimen is equal to 100 MPa√m. This forms the premise of the approach prescribed by ASTM 1921 to determine the ductile-to-brittle transition reference temperature T_0 for ferritic steels.

Thus, by estimating the characteristic material parameter T_0 , (i.e. the ductile to brittle transition reference temperature) the fracture toughness in the DBTT regime can be determined from Equation 5 which can be subsequently used to inform Equation 1.

To achieve this, the ASTM E1921 methodology first requires evaluation of $K_{JC(\text{med})}$ (derived from $K_{JC(i)}$ at selected temperature(s)). The reference temperature T_0 is then evaluated either using the single temperature approach (which can be used if the $K_{JC(\text{med})}$ values are determined at a single test temperature) or multi-temperature approach (which can be used if the $K_{JC(\text{med})}$ values are determined at multiple test temperatures).

For a single temperature approach, the reference temperature can be estimated using an effective value of $K_{JC(\text{med})}$ (derived from $K_{JC(i)}$ (as described in ASTM E1921 Section 10.4) through tests carried out at a single temperature 'T' by re-arranging the terms in Equation 5 as follows

$$T_{0Q} = T - \left(\frac{1}{0.019} \right) \cdot \ln \left(\frac{K_{JC(\text{med})} - 30}{70} \right)$$

Equation 6

For a multi-temperature approach, the reference temperature T_0 is evaluated through an iterative procedure using the equation below

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta_i \frac{\exp[0.019(T_i - T_{0Q})]}{11 + 77\exp[0.019(T_i - T_{0Q})]} - \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{(K_{JC(i)} - 20)^4 \exp[0.019(T_i - T_{0Q})]}{\{11 + 77\exp[0.019(T_i - T_{0Q})]\}^5} = 0$$

Equation 7

where

N is the number of specimens tested

T_i is the test temperature corresponding to $K_{JC(i)}$

δ_i is either equal to 1 (if datum is an uncensored value) or zero (if datum is a censored value).

T_{0Q} is the initial estimate of the reference temperature which becomes validated as T_0 if the censoring and validation criteria specified in sections 10.3, 10.4 and 10.5 of ASTM E1921 [3] are met.

In particular, two key conditions need to be met for T_{0Q} to be validated as T_0 .

1. The data included in the calculations must be tested within the temperature range of $T - T_0 = \pm 50^\circ\text{C}$.

2.
$$\sum_{i=1}^3 r_i n_i \geq 1$$

Equation 8

where r_i is the number of uncensored data within the i^{th} temperature range and n_i is the specimen weighting factor for the same temperature range as per Table 5 of section 10.3 ASTM E1921 [3]). The selective weighting is given on the premise that the data generated at different test temperatures would give “reduced accuracy” contributions to T_0 .

Furthermore, the ASTM E1921 methodology adapts the flaw distribution assumption applicable to brittle materials and allows for correction of the size (thickness) effect associated with the statistical nature of cleavage fracture; i.e. the larger the thickness the higher the possibility of finding a cleavage promoting particle along the crack. Hence, if the fracture toughness value is derived using non-standard specimens (i.e. any size other than 1T), the ASTM E1921 approach proposes a correction to convert the actual K_{JC} value into the corresponding $K_{JC(1T)}$, using the following equation

$$K_{JC(1T)} = 20 + [K_{JC} - 20](B/25.4)^{(1/4)}$$

Equation 9

(where B is the thickness of the tested specimen).

Using the 1T equivalent toughness values at a given temperature, the reference transition temperature T_0 is evaluated according to standard as for 1T specimen.

4.3 Specimen size considerations

4.3.1 Introduction

A key challenge to be addressed from the viewpoint of material property characterisation is to ensure that the property measured from material testing is a characteristic of the material and not of the specimen geometry. For a specimen used to measure the value of fracture toughness at the onset of unstable fracture, this criterion is satisfied when the toughness measured is the lower limiting value, i.e. the value produced when failure occurs in plane strain conditions, with the crack tip stress field characterised by the elastic parameter K [8]. This can be achieved so long as conditions conducive to high constraint, small scale yielding (SSY), and cleavage fracture micro-mechanisms dominate.

The evaluation of the fracture toughness within the DBTT is to be achieved via the elastic–plastic parameter K_{Jc} . This parameter is derived from the (total) J integral at the onset of cleavage fracture (J_c) through Equation 10 below

$$K_{Jc} = \left[J_c \frac{E}{(1-\nu^2)} \right]^{0.5}$$

Equation 10

where E is Young’s modulus and ν is Poisson’s ratio.

The theoretical equations governing the estimation of the crack tip stress field are elaborated in the FRACTESUS Technical Memorandum [8]. The key point to note is that the stress field ahead of the crack tip (crack opening stress) can be characterised by a single parameter ‘ K ’ only if the cracking initiates close enough to the pre-crack tip (i.e. the distance ‘ r ’ from the initial crack tip is much less than the initial crack length ‘ a ’). Under plane strain conditions, cracks extend on the plane normal to the maximum tensile stress and unstable crack extension initiates at a fixed value of critical strain energy release rate G_{crit} which allows it to be used as a material-characterising parameter, which is not possible if plane stress conditions prevail. G_{crit} under plane strain conditions is lower than that under plane stress conditions for most materials in specimens more than a fraction of a mm thick, which makes it a lower bound value as well as a material-characterising value thus satisfying the requirement stated above.

4.3.2 Testing validation requirements

In a specimen of finite size, loaded for plane strain in the central region, plane stress still exists at the specimen edges since no stress exists normal to a free surface. The specimen needs to have a minimum thickness, such that the plane stress regions in the material edges would overlap impacting the plane strain stress field at the specimen centre. This would lead to a plane stress dominated failure mode characterised by “slant” fracture as detailed in the FRACTESUS Technical Memorandum [8]. Additionally, the ligament ahead of the crack tip should be sufficiently large such that the expansion of the plastic zone due to the presence of the front and back faces of the specimen is negligible.

ASTM E399 [1] requires the following criterion to be met for the fracture toughness test to be valid as it would ensure that the plastic zone size at the onset of unstable cracking is limited to only a few percent (~2%) of the ligament length and thus can be considered to have no interaction with either the front or back faces of the sample [8].

$$B, b_0 \geq 2.5(K_Q/\sigma_y)^2$$

Equation 11

With increasing thickness, the relative importance of the edges decreases, the proportion of slant fracture diminishes and the overall value of G_{crit} approaches the low value characteristic of plane strain as described below in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Influence of specimen thickness on G_{crit} [8]

It also needs to be noted, as advised in the FRACTESUS Technical Memorandum [8], the weakest link size correction obtained through Equation 9, applies in the transition regime, in which fracture is a weakest link process. This assumption may no longer apply on the lower shelf where the fracture may proceed from multiple sites. It is thus recommended that size corrections are not performed for lower shelf test temperatures (e.g. $T_0 - 50^\circ\text{C}$) or below a threshold fracture toughness level (e.g. $50 \text{ MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$).

4.4 Data censoring considerations

4.4.1 Cut off value for K_{JC} ($K_{JC\text{limit}}$)

ASTM E1921 [3] stipulates that the maximum K_{JC} capacity ($K_{JC\text{limit}}$) is limited by the specimen's remaining ligament (b_0) as indicated in Equation 12 below. The K_{JC} data that exceeds this limit must be replaced (censored) by the value of the $K_{JC\text{limit}}$.

$$K_{JC\text{limit}} = \left[\frac{Eb_0\sigma_y}{30 \cdot (1 - \nu^2)} \right]^{0.5}$$

Equation 12

The above criterion ensures that tests which may not be valid within the purview of ASTM E399 [1] (from the viewpoint of providing an acceptable value of fracture toughness) may still be valuable from a statistical viewpoint. Thus, the ASTM E1921 methodology provides the option whereby valid measurements taken in the lower transition can be used with invalid measurements in the mid-transition to define the full ductile-to-brittle transition [8].

The $K_{JClimit}$ and K_Q requirement in ASTM E1921 and defined above are intended to denote the maximum allowable toughness at which the calculated K_{JC} is unaffected by constraint loss [3], [13]. Although the constant '30' in Equation 12 (designed as 'M') is deemed suitable for CT specimen geometries, the value may need to be altered for other geometries since otherwise, it could lead to geometry-dependent estimates of the master curve reference temperature T_0 . Usage of CT specimens is hence recommended when a geometry-insensitive T_0 value and the associated master curve are desired [14]. It has been highlighted in FRACTESUS Deliverable D1.1 [7] that $M = 30$ is based on experimental data sets which showed clear changes in T_0 when $M < 30$.

Furthermore, it can be deduced that Equation 12 will be equivalent to Equation 11 if the yield strength is about $(1/12)^{th}$ of the Young's modulus (for $M = 30$). At higher yield strengths, it would appear that Equation 11 may provide a more conservative estimate of $K_{JClimit}$. As discussed in the FRACTESUS Technical Memorandum [8], lower yield strength will result in loss of SSY conditions and a potential overestimation of K_{IC} . This would ultimately result in an underestimation of the transition temperature. This is because when specimen yielding is no longer constrained to SSY conditions, the loss of triaxiality encourages plasticity, increasing local strains while reducing local stresses. Ductile failure then occurs in small specimens when brittle failure would occur in specimens large enough to retain SSY. This shift to the higher-energy failure mode further increases the K_Q measured at a given temperature. In a material within the ductile-to-brittle transition region, this increase in K_Q decreases the apparent transition temperature.

Potential routes to mitigate the problem of extensive data censoring unnecessary through introducing a large-scale yielding (LSY) correction (i.e. the fracture model-based reduction of high apparent K_{JC} values) were investigated within the FRACTESUS project. Two methods in particular were examined within FRACTESUS at NNL [15] and SCK CEN [16]. The NNL approach was based on Nevalainen and Dodds' stress-based model of fracture [17]. There are two aspects to Nevalainen and Dodds' correction: the first refers to the reduction in the driving force for crack extension caused by plasticity at the back face of the specimen and the edges of the specimen; the second refers to the reduction in the effective width of the crack front. It was observed that application of the 'Nevalainen and Dodds' correction led to a small improvement in the comparability of the K_{JC} between small and large specimen data. The SCK method was based on Ruggieri and Dodds' [18] implementation of Wallin et al's [19] stress- and strain-based model of fracture. Li et al [16] found that K_{JC} data corrected using this methodology exhibited a more reasonable distribution around the 5% and 95% Master curve confidence bounds. Thus, the SCK CEN approach may be considered to be the recommended best practice for introducing the large-scale yielding correction.

It was observed in FRACTESUS Deliverable 5.5 [20] that the inclusion or exclusion of censored K_{JC} data can lead to a significant change of T_0 . Specifically, excluding data that would otherwise be censored shifts T_0 to higher temperatures and the effect becomes more pronounced with increasing ratio r/N (where r is the number of uncensored valid data and N is the total number of valid data). Hence, it has been recommended that, in addition to using the $\sum n_i r_i \geq 1$ criterion (see Equation 8) to assess whether the K_{JC} dataset contained sufficient uncensored data to permit calculation of a valid T_0 value, a further restriction $r/N > 0.5$ should be applied. Also, although ASTM E1921 only provides the specimen weighting factor up to a test temperature

of ($T_0 - 50\text{ °C}$), the possibility of using data from lower test temperatures by adopting a suitable weighting factor (e.g. 1/12 for $T_0 - 60\text{ °C}$) can be investigated further.

4.4.2 Crack size limits

To account for the possibility of stable crack extension prior to fracture, the size constraints imposed should ensure SSY conditions. i.e. the crack tip plastic zone should be small and fully constrained being bounded by an elastic region allowing little interaction of the plastic zone with the back face. This will ensure that the growing crack remains predominantly in plane strain and progresses by flat fracture. If the crack-tip plastic zone interacts with the back face, then the process zone becomes so large that failure is by net section collapse rather than by stable crack extension, rendering the use of plane strain fracture criteria redundant. Hence, for plane strain conditions to be realised, the crack tip should be sufficiently deep within the specimen.

To address this, ASTM E1921 [3] mandates the below margin for the initial crack size to balance the requirements for a deep crack (to avoid interactions between the crack tip plastic zone and the front face of the specimen) and a large ligament (to avoid interactions between the crack tip plastic zone and the back face of the specimen).

$$0.45 \leq a_0/w \leq 0.55$$

Equation 13

Experience within FRACTESUS showed that, in laboratories with experience in manufacturing and testing 0.16T CTs, a majority of specimens met the pre-crack size requirement. Conversely, inexperienced laboratories encountered difficulties in meeting the requirement. The FRACTESUS recommendation is hence that rigorous training programs are instated to ensure that suitably qualified and experienced personnel are assigned to campaigns of 0.16T CTs testing of material of limited availability.

In addition, it was reported in FRACTESUS Deliverable 5.5 [20] that the limiting pre-crack length value could be increased to $a/W < 0.60$ without compromising the accuracy of the reference temperature calculations. However, this will result in a reduced initial ligament size thereby reducing $K_{JClimit}$. Aiming for a maximum pre-crack length up to $0.6W$ may, therefore, merely replace measurements censored as a result of an excessively long pre-crack with measurements censored for exceeding the small-scale yielding limit. As an aside, it was also indicated in [21] that specimen type or size has minimal effect on the distribution of the crack initiation location so long as the ASTM E1921 requirement for initial crack size is met.

As a stable crack extends, the widths of the regions failing by slant fracture increase and the plastic zone size increases making it difficult to maintain cracking dominated by plane strain SSY conditions. Hence, it is necessary to define not only the initial specimen geometry and starting crack length, but also a maximum ductile crack length, beyond which the brittle fracture measurements cease to be characteristic of the material and the corresponding K_{Jc} value is censored by the highest uncensored K_{Jc} value of the whole dataset as highlighted in the FRACTESUS Technical Memorandum [8]. ASTM E1921 also stipulates that the limiting size of the crack under ductile growth must be the lower of $0.05(W-a_0)$ or 1 mm for the test results to be valid. If the maximum crack growth criterion is violated, the K_{Jc} value also shall be regarded as invalid and replaced with the highest valid K_{Jc} in the data set for any specimen size in the censoring procedure.

It has however, been highlighted in FRACTESUS Deliverable 5.5 [20] that inclusion of this crack growth criterion results only in a small increase in T_0 as compared to the case when only

the $K_{JClimit}$ censoring criterion is considered. The reason for this is that specimens with ductile crack growth also exceed the $K_{JClimit}$ value in almost all cases, and the difference between $K_{JClimit}$ and $K_{JC\Delta a}$ is moderate in larger test series. It was concluded in FRACTESUS Deliverable 5.5 [20] that the impact of the crack growth censoring criterion on T_0 is likely to be insignificant. The FRACTESUS recommendation is that the $K_{JClimit}$ criterion can be considered as the overriding constraint, which would bound the crack growth criterion and hence a separate consideration of the limiting size of the crack growth is not deemed necessary.

4.5 Test temperature considerations

ASTM E1921 [3] recommends that the test temperature should be close to that at which the $K_{JC(med)}$ value is close to $100 \text{ MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$ for the specimen size selected and mandates the use of the data distributed over a temperature range of $T_0 \pm 50^\circ\text{C}$. For small specimens, tests at $T_{KJC}=100\text{MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$ will generally exceed the validity limit associated with the loss of small-scale yielding and small specimens would tend to be constrained by lower values of $K_{JClimit}$. As noted in FRACTESUS Deliverable 5.5 [20], testing temperatures close to T_0 may lead to censoring due to K_{JC} exceeding the $K_{JClimit}$ and/or violating the maximum acceptable crack growth highlighted in section 4.4.2. Hence it would be necessary to carry out the tests at relatively low temperatures.

On the other hand, testing at too low temperatures ($T - T_0 < 50^\circ\text{C}$) also leads to invalid data. Moreover, as noted in the FRACTESUS Technical Memorandum [8], since the onset of the transition is gradual, the closer the valid points are pushed to the lower shelf, the more difficult it becomes to identify the onset of the transition (i.e. greater uncertainty in T_0). In order to compensate for this, there would be a need to test a large number of samples since the uncertainty of T_0 is inversely proportional to the square root of the number of uncensored specimens, as shown before in Equation 3. This concern is exacerbated in the case of miniature specimens, where due to specimens tested being smaller and less material surface being tested within one test, there is a higher likelihood of local material inhomogeneities affecting the measurements.

Hence a strategic approach has been proposed in FRACTESUS Deliverable 5.5 [20] to estimate the test temperature for a preferred target censoring probability (relative frequency of censored data) using an equation that relates the test temperature to the target censoring probability and a preliminary estimate of T_0 ($T_{0, estimated}$). The final value of T_0 can then be evaluated by carrying out tests at preferred target temperatures.

$T_{0, estimated}$ can typically be evaluated using Charpy tests (T_{41J}) as described in ASTM E1921 Section 8.4.1. A controlled approach can be used to carry out the tests whereby, an initial approximate value of T_0 ($T_{0,exp}$) is evaluated by setting K_{JC} to $K_{JClimit}$ value (derived corresponding to a selected test temperature using Equation 12) and evaluating the $T_{0,exp}$ from Equation 2. Using this value of $T_{0,exp}$, three to five tests can be carried out within an acceptable test temperature window to arrive at $T_{0, estimated}$.

In theory, the test temperature window for the initial set of tests ($T_{test} - T_{0,exp}$) can be evaluated by first estimating the $K_{JC,0.16T}$ equivalent of $K_{JC(med),1T}$ of $100 \text{ MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$ using Equation 9. This equivalent $K_{JC,0.16T}$ value can then be used along with P_f of 0.5 in Equation 2 to estimate ($T_{test} - T_{0,exp}$). However, experience acquired within FRACTESUS and elsewhere led to the recommendation in FRACTESUS Deliverable D5.5 [20] that the first set of tests (to evaluate $T_{0, estimated}$) should be carried out in the range $-30^\circ\text{C} < T_{test} - T_{0,exp} < -25^\circ\text{C}$.

Using the value determined for $T_{0, \text{estimated}}$ the next set of tests should be performed at preferred temperatures (depending upon the target censoring probability) as per Equation 14 below to evaluate the final value of T_0 .

$$T = T_{0, \text{estimated}} - T_{\text{sh}} + \frac{1}{c} \cdot \arctan \left[\frac{P_{c, \text{trg}} - 0.5}{0.5} \right]$$

Equation 14

where $T_{\text{sh}} = 7.9 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and $c = 0.056$ are constants derived from a large dataset (including FRACTESUS data) and $P_{c, \text{trg}}$ is the target probability of a K_{JC} measurement requiring censoring (e.g. 0.05-0.95).

The censoring probability in turn is evaluated considering two parameters, $s_{rn} = \sum r_i n_i$ and r/N calculated from the available test data which is detailed further in FRACTESUS Deliverable 5.5 [20].

4.6 Material homogeneity considerations

4.6.1 Observations from FRACTESUS on inhomogeneity aspects

Work reported in FRACTESUS Technical Memorandum [4] highlighted that the assumption of K_{JC} distribution at a given test temperature being dependant only upon the size / strength distribution of the population of weak links is valid only for a homogeneous distribution of a single population of links, which may not hold true for inhomogeneous microstructure. This has also been recognised in [13] where was suggested that significant macroscopic inhomogeneity often means deviation from the statistical cleavage fracture model and the ASTM E1921 requirements based on the weakest link theory (which assumes randomly distributed defects or cleavage fracture initiators in the material). Such materials typically exhibit anomalously scattered fracture toughness in the transition region appearing as deviations in respect of the standard tolerance bound.

Broadly speaking, the ASTM E1921 MC approach relies on a principle of similitude which necessitates minimal differences in basic microstructural constitution (or equivalent variability in constituent grain distribution) between different specimens. Hence, establishing material homogeneity between 0.16T CT and 1T CT samples in an equivalent manner is crucial for scaling of the K_{JC} value derived from miniature specimens using Equation 9.

Work reported in the FRACTESUS Technical Memorandum [4] presents comparisons between the basic T_0 measurements derived from large and small specimens. It was concluded that despite using some reasonable statistical adjustments, there were still notable differences between T_0 values derived from 0.16T CT specimens and those from actual 1T specimens in two of the six steels investigated (JRQ and 73W). Following a review, it was suggested that these discrepancies could not be attributed to differences in specimen size or test temperature and instead, it is highly likely that the disparity could be attributable to aspects relating to material inhomogeneity.

In the 73W steel, for instance, it was identified that there were more than one family of weak links which were not interspersed homogeneously. Instead, they were separated into different microstructural constituents whose distribution could in turn be influenced by the specimen size. Specifically, it was identified that the more brittle family may always be present in the

plastic zone of a 1T CT specimen but may or may not be present within the plastic zone of a miniature specimen.

Furthermore, a study of the JRQ steel results indicated that the differences in T_0 estimates were more marked between 0.4T CT and 1T CT specimens compared to the differences in the values between 0.16T CT and 0.4T CT specimens. Based on a closer examination of the microstructure, it was concluded that the constituent which shifts and broadens the distribution of T_0 values derived from 1T JRQ data appeared to be associated with inhomogeneity on a larger scale than the features seen in the microstructural examination.

Another observation highlighted in the FRACTESUS Technical Memorandum [4] indicated that the scale of the inhomogeneity in a weld was such that a 1T CT would sample about 15 weld beads while a 0.16T CT would sample less than one weld bead, which suggest that both base and weld metals can be microstructurally inhomogeneous on a scale relevant to toughness samples.

Thus, in other words, the length scale of the inhomogeneity determined whether changing the size of the specimen affected the measurement of T_0 and scatter. The size scales of inhomogeneity in the RPV steels examined could vary significantly, affecting the relationship between T_0 values derived from 0.16T and larger specimens or between 0.4T (possibly even 1T) and larger specimens. It is thus important to know when simple methods of using toughness data from miniature specimens will predict material properties adequately, and when additional care will be required from the viewpoint of material inhomogeneity.

4.6.2 ASTM E1921 inhomogeneity screening approach

Section 10.6 of ASTM E1921 [3] provides guidelines and criterion to screen for material inhomogeneity through a quantitative approach. Appendix X5 of ASTM E1921 [3] provides alternative ways of describing the bounds if the data set is deemed to be inhomogeneous and the procedure has been summarised in the FRACTESUS Technical Memorandum [4].

ASTM E1921 clearly asserts that at least 20 K_{Jc} values are needed to have reasonable confidence in the screening criterion for macroscopic inhomogeneity in order to ensure that the sample population captures both a) the possibility of differences in the fracture toughness between low and higher toughness material constituents and b) the relative amounts of the lower and higher toughness constituents is more equivalent.

However, identification of a dataset as inhomogeneous (or a failure to identify inhomogeneity) on this basis must be accepted with caution as advised in FRACTESUS Technical Memorandum [4]. If the dataset fails the screening criteria stipulated in Section 10.6 of ASTM E1921, then ASTM E1921 recommends other steps in Appendix X5 to carry out the screening depending upon the size of the data set with further distinctions dependent upon whether the sample set is bi-modal (i.e. containing two toughness populations) or multi-modal (i.e. containing randomly distributed toughness populations).

4.6.3 Observations from application of inhomogeneity screening

Application of the ASTM E1921 screening criteria to JRQ and 73W specimens reported in the FRACTESUS Technical Memorandum [4] indicated that while about 2/3rd of the 0.16T CT samples were deemed to be inhomogeneous, the corresponding fraction for 1T CT specimens was only 1/3rd. It was concluded that the scales of the material inhomogeneities in the RPV steels examined were such that 0.16T CTs are likely to sample a single type of microstructure, which may not be the more brittle constituent, while larger specimens will

sample a more representative range of microstructures. Also, if insufficient material from the weaker constituent is present, then the toughness measurement in the small sample will reflect the population of weak links in the less brittle constituent.

When the scale of the material inhomogeneity is such that only large crack fronts sample both more and less brittle constituents, the range of mini- T_0 values is a non-conservative predictor of the range of large- T_0 values. Furthermore, depending on the scale of the material inhomogeneity, consistency between 0.16T and 0.4T or 0.5T data may or may not predicate consistency between $<1T$ and $\geq 1T$ specimen data. In other words, the change in behaviour may not necessarily occur between 0.16T and larger specimens but could occur between 0.4T or 0.5T and larger specimens, depending on the material. Hence it is important to identify the effects of the scale and prevalence of the weaker microstructural constituent (family of links) on the relation between small and large specimens.

Results on K_{JC} values indicated that with a large population of 0.16T CTS-derived K_{JC} data, even a simple inhomogeneity screening could result in the lower bound curve from Equation 2 bounding most of the 1T CT data (with the acceptance becoming even more favourable if the margin adjustment is implemented). As identified in the FRACTESUS Technical Memorandum [4], conducting a full inhomogeneity analysis on large data sets (as prescribed in Appendix 5.3 of ASTM E1921) can result in the best fit line through the plot of the T_0 estimates of 0.16T CT specimens against those from large specimens becoming closer to one to one. Also, the DBTT values estimated from 0.16T CT are within an acceptable factor (in standard deviation) of the corresponding values from large specimens. The bounds derived from the full inhomogeneity analyses, whether bimodal or multimodal, would hence be fully conservative and more preferable.

Also, as noted in the FRACTESUS Technical Memorandum [4], both base metals and welds are likely to contain more than one constituent in islands of diameters of the order fractions of a mm – several mm (e.g. recrystallised and as-deposited regions of a weld bead, islands of ferrite / bainite / martensite reflecting the dendrite spacing of castings). Each constituent will contain a population of weak links and the distributions of strengths in the different populations may or may not overlap. Hence, if material inhomogeneity is suspected over long length scales, then specimens should be cut from widely separated locations to enhance the likelihood of picking up representative levels of inhomogeneity.

For steels that may not necessarily follow the ASTM E1921 Master curve, there may be a possibility of describing the data as a weighted sum of Master curves with different T_0 values. The distribution of the toughness data could then be regarded as synonymous to a microstructurally inhomogeneous material in which each constituent follows the Master curve. Therefore, adopting the best practices developed within FRACTESUS to accommodate inhomogeneity at different length scales should address such cases.

4.7 Sample set size considerations

Based on a statistical study on data pertaining to unirradiated 15Kh2MFAA, 73W and JRQ samples, it has been recommended in FRACTESUS Deliverable 5.5 [20] that for a target standard deviation of $\sigma_{T_0} < 7^\circ\text{C}$ as a “reasonable” value, the required minimum number of data points for a T_0 analysis would be at least ≥ 16 . This is also consistent with the observation made in [21], which suggests that for low upper-shelf materials, testing at least more than 15 specimens is recommended. While this number of specimens would allow the predicted T_0 to converge to a consistent value for the dataset, it may not necessarily lead to a value of T_0

which is directly comparable with measurements on larger samples if the steel investigated is inhomogeneous (or does not follow the Master curve).

The best practice suggested within the FRACTESUS Technical Memorandum [4] from the analysis of 0.16T data is to test at least 30 samples of 0.16T CTSs so that a reliable assessment of inhomogeneity can be performed according to ASTM E1921 Appendix X5. The analysis of T_m (the temperature at which the median toughness is $100 \text{ MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$ in an inhomogeneous dataset analysed according to the multimodal Master curve method) and σ_{T_m} – margin-adjusted 5% lower bound are then likely to be representative of data from larger specimens.

If fewer specimens are available such that the refined approaches from ASTM E1921 cannot be applied, it has been recommended in the FRACTESUS Technical Memorandum [4] to use simpler methods (but with at least 16 samples) but increase the magnitude of σ associated with T_0 by an uncertainty associated with material inhomogeneity (in which the $\sigma_{\text{material variability}}$ is taken as at least 7°C for a base metal or 19°C for a weld).

$$\sigma_{\text{total}}^2 = \sigma_{T_0}^2 + \sigma_{\text{material variability}}^2$$

Equation 15

Extrapolation using the $2\sigma_{T_0}$ margin adjustment to $T_{0\text{scrm}}$ would then provide a reasonable description of the 5% lower bound to the 1T data.

4.8 Irradiation effects

For characterization of irradiated material behaviour using measurements taken from irradiated samples, the following caveats must be taken into consideration [12]:

1. The state of mechanical constraint in the specimens used to measure fracture toughness may not match the mechanical constraint on a flaw in the vessel.
2. The irradiation conditions of the surveillance material may not match the conditions of interest in the vessel. While differences in neutron fluence are commonly recognized, other factors such as neutron flux or irradiation temperature may also contribute to discrepancies between the vessel and sample material.
3. The radiation sensitivity of the pressure vessel steels is controlled by small variations in impurity elements (e.g. Cu and P), which can vary significantly within a single heat of material.

Also, as indicated in [13], irradiation induced microstructural changes in the material may affect not only the re-distribution of alloying and impurity elements, but also the fracture mode. If the fracture mode changes from cleavage to intergranular fracture or quasi-cleavage, it would imply that the cleavage fracture model in its basic form, tends to become gradually more inaccurate.

4.9 Specimen fabrication considerations

One of the key issues with miniaturizing toughness specimens is the resulting increasing difficulty of machining and aligning small specimens within acceptable tolerances. The acceptable tolerances on all dimensions in a CT specimen is mandated by ASTM E1820 as \pm

0.013 W (Figure 3) [8]. This equals to about ± 0.10 mm for a 0.16T CT specimen. This is very narrow, especially when specimens need to be fabricated in hot cell conditions.

Figure 3. Acceptable Compact Tension Specimen (CT) geometries [8].

It is recommended that to notice issues during fabrication, as well as other stages of in-cell work, a well-designed camera system is used. Also, for a successful pre-cracking, it has to be ensured that the holes for the load pins are precisely aligned, i.e. exactly perpendicular to the specimen's side faces. Specimen fabrication may be done by EDM or classical milling.

Table 2 below provides a comparison of the relative advantages and drawbacks of the two approaches.

Table 2. Advantages and drawbacks of EDM and classical milling [20].

	EDM	Milling
Precision	High overall accuracy but less control with respect to sharp angles.	Less overall accuracy but high accuracy with respect to sharp angles. Accurate and consistent notch radii when using a dedicated milling head. The milling heads wear off and loose accuracy over time.
Human error	As little as two times clamping/centering of the test piece. Little human intervention needed and less probability for errors.	Up to five to six times clamping/centering of the test piece. A lot of human intervention needed and more probability for errors.
Efficiency	Easy to machine a series of samples in one go. Largely automated. Up to two times faster than milling.	Every sample is machined individually. Labor intensive. Up to two times slower than EDM.
Finish	Cu implantation and stronger oxidation of the surface	
Maintenance	Considerable amount of used wire as active waste; regular change of filters for waste water.	Milling heads lose precision due to wear.

To ensure “straightness” of the pre-crack front, ASTM E1921 also imposes a criterion which requires that the average starting fatigue pre-crack size derived from the physical measurements post-testing (as described in ASTM E1921 section 8.8.1) does not differ from each physical measurement by more than $0.1(b_0B_N)^{1/2}$. However, it was concluded in FRACTESUS Deliverable 5.5 [20] that inclusion of data from specimens with “invalid” pre-crack shape (based on the above requirement), does not excessively affect the reference temperature. If there is otherwise insufficient data to derive a valid T_0 (more likely when irradiated materials are investigated), the inclusion of those data could be useful.

It has been highlighted in FRACTESUS Deliverable 5.5 [20] that fatigue pre-cracking with crack opening displacement (COD) measured at the front face provides acceptable crack fronts while the COD measurement at the load-line during pre-cracking turned out to be unreliable, especially at high fatigue frequencies (potentially due to test frame vibrations and other factors). If the estimation of crack length by unloading compliance measurement turns out to be unreliable, it should be combined with optical measurements at the specimen.

Furthermore, side-grooving can be used to achieve crack front straightness and maintain plane strain conditions towards the side faces (as it helps to homogenize the maximum principal stress in the ligament and increase the stress triaxiality along the specimen thickness thus promoting crack propagation initiation along the entire length of the effective section area). However, it was reported in FRACTESUS deliverables 2.1 [9] and 5.5 [20] that the effect of side grooving on the reference temperature was insignificant and hence the omission of side grooves is possible which would save fabrication work, in particular under hot-cell conditions.

4.10 Testing considerations

Testing specifications of ASTM E1921 refer extensively to the more established ASTM standards such as E399 and E1820. As such, these standards should be regarded important sources of information for fracture mechanical testing of compact tension specimens.

The equation below is typically used to convert the front face displacement to load line displacement based on a virtual rotation point as advised in FRACTESUS Deliverable 5.5 [20].

$$\frac{LLD}{FFD} = \frac{a + r \cdot (W - a)}{a + r \cdot (W - a) + X} = \frac{a/W + r \cdot (1 - a/W)}{a/W + r \cdot (1 - a/W) + X/W}$$

Equation 16

The parameters associated with Equation 16 are described in Figure 4 below.

Figure 4. Geometry parameters for the FFD-LLD conversion

It has been observed in FRACTESUS Deliverable 5.5 [20] that while ASTM E1921 recommends an LLD/FFD ratio of 0.73, this is only valid for $a/W \approx 0.5$ and $X/W=0.25$. This is not always true in case of mini-CT specimens and Equation 16 should be used instead. It has been recommended that the rotational factor $r=0.352$ is better for small pin displacements (<0.6 mm), and $r=0.5$ should be used above this value to keep K_I error below 2%.

Section 8.7.1 of ASTM E1921 [3] provides guidelines for ascertaining the loading rate to carry out the test. A dK/dt range of 0.1 to 2.0 $\text{MPa}\sqrt{\text{m/s}}$ is proposed, which ensures that the test is conducted at a rate which allows obtaining T_0 which is insensitive to the loading rate within 10 °C. This was corroborated in [21] which reported that so long as the above validity criterion is honoured, no significant changes were observed in T_0 due to variations in the loading rate.

5 CONCLUSIONS

ASTM E1921 [3] provides a methodology to estimate the DBTT as the Master Curve reference temperature, T_0 which can then be used to quantify both the variation of the median value of fracture toughness with temperature and the scatter of fracture toughness about this median value. Using this, T_0 can be determined with relatively few fracture tests and a low volume of material. Furthermore, the standard also contains a procedure for assessing whether the distribution of toughness measurements indicates that the material tested is homogeneous and provides alternative ways of describing the bounds if the data set is inhomogeneous.

A key concern raised by FRACTESUS project stakeholders associated with adoption of the ASTM E1921 methodology for miniature specimens is a lack of adequate evidence to demonstrate sufficient relevance and applicability of the test results to RPV steels (at a component scale). Among other issues, the narrow test temperature window for miniature specimens and material homogeneity equivalency considerations necessitates a careful extrapolation of the results from miniature specimen testing to describe the full ductile-to-brittle transition characteristics of RPV steels at a component scale through a clear understanding of the underpinning theoretical basis associated with the ASTM E1921 methodology.

To that end, this report has provided an account of the pivotal insights generated by the FRACTESUS project into the practical hurdles that may need to be confronted and harmonized with the overall philosophy underpinning the ASTM E1921 methodology. These can be used to introduce empirical adjustments to the ASTM E1921 methodology to more accurately extrapolate the test results from miniature specimens for fracture behaviour characterization of RPV steels in the DBTT regime. In addition, the key constraints and caveats underscoring different aspects relating to application of the ASTM E1921 MC approach were identified.

It is envisioned that the observations, findings and recommendations from the FRACTESUS project will serve as crucial guidelines to inform future initiatives pertaining to fracture toughness evaluation in the DBTT regime using miniature specimens to ensure optimality of the conclusions and decisions pertaining to structural integrity assessments of reactor components.

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